

MAPPING POLICY OPTIONS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY COMMUNITIES IN EUROPE

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Introduction

Consumer (co-)ownership in renewable energy (RE) is an essential ingredient of the overall success of the transition to a low-carbon economy and society in Europe. When consumers acquire ownership in RE projects, they can become prosumers generating a part of the energy they consume. Thus, reducing their overall energy costs, while at the same time potentially generating additional income, through the sale of excess production. Yet, becoming a prosumer requires availability of time, headspace and access to substantial upfront investment, as well as access to information and knowledge of the various possible options. This creates burdens for many EU citizens, especially vulnerable groups, including women, who are underrepresented in technological industries, and those who are of low-income, energy poor or low-educated.

The recast of the *Renewable Energy Directive* (RED II) adopted in the end of 2018 as part of the *Clean Energy Package for all Europeans* marks a turning point for energy communities in the EU and paves a way for a more decentralised and citizen-oriented form of energy transition in Europe. A key novel feature of RED II is the **right for communities, cooperatives and individuals to produce, consume, store and sell their own RE**, without facing excessive charges or

KEY POINTS

- The *Renewable Energy Directive II* paves the way for a **decentralised and citizen-oriented** energy transition in Europe. It gives a new set of rights for communities and individuals to produce, consume, store and trade their own renewable energy. Yet, individual consumers and communities still face significant challenges rooted in both the transposition of the *Clean Energy Package* and the specific national contexts.
- Major barriers are related to: **different national legal frameworks** for the promotion of renewable energy source; **frequent changes in regulation, support schemes and financing opportunities**; **information gaps**; **limited access to finance**; **discriminatory grid regulation**; and **incoherence with national social policies**.
- Common challenges remain the **unequal access to ancillary services and capacity markets**; the divergent legal forms of Renewable Energy Communities across different EU MSs; the **technological challenge** of balancing demand with geographically dispersed, intermittent RES; as well as the **transaction costs** associated with integrating **small- and medium-size actors**, accompanied by complex regulations. These common EU-wide challenges could be overcome with a **uniform improvement of the administrative capacity, financial incentives** and altogether **better governance** of the energy system.
- There is a need for a **EU-wide specific strategy** to be transposed and integrated into the national regulatory frameworks that should aim at **understanding the needs of the local communities**, identifying the **key stakeholders**, as well as reaching out to **vulnerable consumers** and engaging them.
- SCORE facilitates co-ownership of renewables by **piloting a novel and inclusive financial model** (*Consumer Stock Ownership Plan*) in three EU countries, thus demonstrating new forms of Renewable Energy Communities with an inclusion of vulnerable consumers.

administrative barriers.¹ Before, consumers could not rely to a great extent on support at the EU-level and were dependent on local or national regulations that either differed among Member States (MS) or were subjected to frequent changes. Energy citizens, whether individual prosumers, cooperatives, communities or small-scale ‘ecopreneurs’, still have a long way to go before establishing their role as fully-fledged participants in the Just Transition process. This is especially so in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) where the benefits of such ownership forms are less known and yet to be explored due to structural deficiencies. Energy transition scenarios in CEE are often associated with expensive energy prices, against a background of widespread energy poverty,² and preferential energy subsidies for large, politically backed-up fossil-fuel dependent energy sectors. All of which has stifled the market for renewable energy communities.³

The transposition of the RED II, the enhanced climate conditionality of the next *Multiannual Financial Framework (2021 – 2027)* and the 2018 regulation on EU funding mechanism, in its part on community-led local development, provide new avenues for the creation and strengthening of energy communities and a shift towards more decentralised and prosumer-oriented ownership models. The benefits of citizen-owned renewable energy projects could be numerous: revitalising local economies and increasing social capital, increasing public acceptance of energy transition alternatives, promoting regional cooperation and local partnerships, building com-

munity resilience, lowering energy bills, tackling energy poverty, the financial empowerment of vulnerable consumers, as well as its potential to foster technological innovation.

Based upon the findings and conclusions from recent research on the economic, social, technological and governance enabling conditions and barriers in promoting prosumership and renewable energy communities in Europe (ENABLE.EU,⁴ REINVENT,⁵ NEWCOMERS⁶ and PROSEU⁷), an international team of researchers and practitioners⁸ is endeavouring to facilitate the co-ownership in RE. It has done so by piloting a new financial model, the *Consumer Stock Ownership Plan*, in Italy, the Czech Republic and Germany with numerous European cities following.

As a financial instrument, the **Consumer Stock Ownership Plan (CSOP) brings several advantages with regard to the set-up of Renewable Energy Communities (RECs).**⁹ It also provides consumers with flexible participation, external financing and long-term loan repayment, thereby encouraging the engagement of low-income households. The CSOP foresees the creation of an operating company that allows individual consumers to pool their investments together. External financing is used to avoid the recourse to micro-credits for each consumer and raise financial leverage while consumers are able to repay their share of the loan through future earnings from the investment, i.e. the sale of the excess of electricity production (see Figure 1). The CSOP ensures appropriate representation of consumers in the

¹ For details see Lowitzsch, J. 2020. Investing in a Renewable Future – Renewable Energy Communities, Consumer (Co-)Ownership and Energy Sharing in the Clean Energy Package. In: European Energy & Climate Journal, Volume 9.

² EU Energy Poverty Observatory.

³ Bertram, R. & R. Primova (eds). 2018. [Energy Atlas: Facts and figures about renewables in Europe](#). Berlin, Brussels, Luxembourg: Joint Report by Heinrich Böll Stiftung, Friends of the Earth Europe, Green Renewable Energies Federation and Green European Foundation.

⁴ Puka-Kjøde, L. 2019. [D8.5 | ENABLE.EU: Written synthesis of ENABLE.EU’s findings](#), ENABLE.EU.

⁵ N/a (REINVENT).

⁶ Palm, J. et. al. 2020. [Report: D3.1: Description of polycentric settings in the partner countries](#), NEWCOMERS working paper.

⁷ N/a PROSEU.

⁸ ‘Supporting Consumer Ownership in Renewable Energies’ (SCORE) is a coordination and support action, receiving funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

⁹ Lowitzsch, J., 2019. [Consumer Stock Ownership Plans – The Prototype Business Model for Renewable Energy Communities](#). In: *Energies* 13, 118.

Figure 1. Consumer Stock Ownership Plan applied to a Renewable Energy Community

Source: J Lowitzsch 2019 IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci. 290 012051.

operating company via a trusteeship (an individual person or fiduciary entity). This simplifies the daily operations and professionalises decision-making. Thus, it both removes the main barrier for attracting external business investments and ensures flexibility with regards to the entry and exit of consumers into a CSOP. Once the loan has been repaid, the revenue of the RES installation can be distributed to consumers providing an additional source of income.

The EU Regulatory Framework for Renewable Energy Communities

In June 2018, the EU agreed on the major climate and energy framework for 2030 as part of the *Clean Energy Package*, which included an overall binding renewables target of 32% and an indicative energy efficiency target of 32.5%. The RED II and the new *Internal Electricity Market Directive* (IEMD) introduce an innovative legislative framework for RECs author-

ising them for energy/electricity sharing over the public grid. In terms of consumers' rights, the new RED II contains the following key provisions:

- The new legislation reinforces the right of European citizens, local authorities, small businesses and cooperatives to produce, consume, store and sell their own renewable energy, without being subject to punitive taxes or excessive bureaucracy.
- The RED II recognises that for the over 40% of Europeans living in apartment blocks, collective action to install renewable technology may be the best way to benefit from renewable energy.
- Citizens could also get represented through aggregators, a market participant that can pool smaller independent producers together and help them with the optimisation of the use of their installations.
- The new regulatory framework also allows consumers to trade renewable energy between themselves without an intermediary (peer-to-peer trading).

- MS have to adopt an enabling framework for prosumership and in particular for defining RECs.

Energy communities are mentioned and defined in both the RED II and the IEMD. The IEMD mainly covers the horizontal level, that is, their rights and obligations towards public authorities, other electricity enterprises and consumers on the electricity markets. RED II complements the IEMD by establishing a vertical dimension that ensures that RECs can compete for support on an equal footing with other market participants and urges MS to “take into account specificities of renewable energy communities when designing support schemes”. The RED II also envisions the **inclusion of low-income and vulnerable households** and defines a “jointly acting renewable self-consumers” for consumers living in the same building, engaging into self-consumption.

The transposition of the RED II raises the question of the form and status energy communities have. Since European energy law does not rule out other private law initiatives, RECs are not considered as the only form of energy communities. At the same time to qualify as REC benefitting from energy sharing and the RED II enabling framework public authorities need other partners. 100% municipal projects would violate the autonomy criterion of the REC (i.e., no single member may have more than 33% of the voting rights) and thus not pass the threshold for a REC under its legal definition.¹⁰ Therefore, **heterogeneity of co-investors becomes a prerequisite in order to benefit from the enabling framework and the opportunity of energy sharing.**¹¹

The Challenges for Renewable Energy Communities in Europe

The transposition of RED II must be accompanied by measures that ensure stakeholders have enough information about the opportunities of RECs, financing opportunities and earmarked capital. These challenges could be overcome with a uniform **improvement of the administrative capacity, financial incentives** and altogether **better governance** of the energy system.

While some bottlenecks are rooted in the transposition of the *Clean Energy Package*,¹² other obstacles are often linked to specific national contexts (e.g., administrative bottlenecks present in some member-states and absent in others).¹³ Although RED II provided MS with an enabling framework for RES communities, the latter needs to incorporate a broader definition that covers the wide spectrum of different REC.¹⁴

National bottlenecks faced by Renewable Energy Communities

The legal and business uncertainty linked to frequent changes in regulations, support schemes and financing opportunities at national level have been highlighted as the main challenges in the development of RECs throughout the different MS. The **retroactive policies and the fluctuating government support** in countries like the Czech Republic, Spain, Poland, Hungary and Bulgaria,¹⁵ as well as renewed state support for traditional energy players (including fossil fuels),

¹⁰ PROSEU, Community Power, SCORE, Renewables Networking Platform, EREF 2020: [Transposition Guidance for citizen energy policies. Recommendations to strengthen prosumers and energy communities when transposing the Clean Energy Package \(RED II, IEMD\)](#).

¹¹ Ibid.

¹² Hoicka, C.E., J. Lowitzsch, M.-C. Brisbois, A. Kumar & L. Ramirez Camargo. 2021 forthcoming. Implementing a just renewable energy transition: Policy advice for transposing the new European rules for Renewable Energy Communities; In: Energy Policy.

¹³ The data here is based on legal and technical due diligence of the pilot cases in IT, CZ and DE, as well as on experts' and citizens' interviews and feedback under the [SCORE project](#).

¹⁴ Lowitzsch, J., C.E. Hoicka, & F.J. van Tulder. 2020. [Renewable energy communities under the 2019 European Clean Energy Package – Governance model for the energy clusters of the future?](#) In: Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews.

¹⁵ Puka-Kjøde, L. 2019. [D8.5 | ENABLE.EU: Written synthesis of ENABLE.EU's findings](#), ENABLE.EU.

have been identified as major barriers blocking the formation and further development of RES communities on the ground. In many Eastern European countries, the **lack of knowledge and facts-based dialogue** on the topic, as well as the **dissemination of counter-narratives** in both the traditional and social media have also contributed to the weak local support for such policies. Last but not least, important **financial and administrative barriers** still remain in place which are slowing down the speed of project development and even, at its worst extent, hindering the very possibility of establishing RECs in EU MS.¹⁶

Different national legal frameworks for the promotion of RES

National legal frameworks, as well as local contexts (e.g. the development of regional energy coopera-

tives in Italy) have shaped, to a great extent, the disparate and fluctuating development of renewable energy communities across countries. Frequent changes in national legislation and retroactive policies on RES support schemes have had a negative impact on the raising of private capital and weakened the RES investing environment (e.g. withdrawal of national incentives for solar and wind energy in the Czech Republic).¹⁷

Progress in the transposition of the RED II is also uneven. While some countries such as Germany, France, Slovenia and Greece have started this process, others are yet to develop a regulatory framework for RECs (e.g. Luxembourg, Poland and Portugal). The inconsistent pace of this transposition and the discretion left to the MS in doing so prevents policy harmonisation and creates a web of complex legal practices in the EU,

Table 1. Overview of RES Legal conditions in the pilot countries (as of December 2019)

	Support Scheme – Electricity		Support Scheme – Heating & Cooling	Policies
	Solar	Biomass		
DE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Special schemes for electricity intensive enterprises; – Special schemes for self-consumption; – Compensation for electricity not fed into the grid due to grid-related bottlenecks; 			German Renewable Energy Sources Act (Erneuerbare Energien Gesetz); Renewable Energies Heat Act (Erneuerbare-Energien-Wärmegesetz); Tenant Electricity Act (Mieterstromgesetz); Local support programs of individual federal states, districts or communities
	Feed-in tariff	Tendering	Subsidies	Training programmes
	Low-interest loans	Flexibility surcharge		Certification Programmes for RES installations
	Supports for the usage of stationary battery storage systems, related to a PV installation			Exemplary role of public authorities
	Market Premium Tariff	Flexibility premium	Loans	Renewable Energy Standard programme supporting networks and accumulators
	Tenant electricity surcharge			RES-H building obligations
	Tendering: solar projects starting from 750 kW			Support of RES-H infrastructure

¹⁶ REN21. 2016. *07 Feature: Community Renewable Energy*, Renewable Global Status Report.

¹⁷ Lowitzsch, J. 2019. *Energy Transition Financing Consumer Co-Ownership in Renewables*. Palgrave Macmillan.

	Support Scheme – Electricity		Support Scheme – Heating & Cooling	Policies
	Solar	Biomass		
IT	Net-metering (cambio sul posto)		Price-based scheme	Training programmes
	Reduction in VAT and real estate tax			Standards and certificate of compliance
	Regional renewable energy programmes		Tax regulation scheme	All new buildings and all buildings undergoing major refurbishment are obliged to integrate RES-E and RES-H
	Premium tariff (ritiro dedicato)			Guarantee fund supporting DHN
CZ	Exemption from Real Estate tax/ Discounted Investment loans		Subsidies (Operational Programme)	Renewable energy use assessment.
	Subsidies (Operational Programme “Environment”)		Exemption from Real Estate Tax	Certification programme for installers

Source: RES LEGAL Europe and SCORE interviews with national experts.

with a high heterogeneity in national legislations. On this point, the **legal definition for REC is considered a major factor that could either limit or create favourable conditions** for the development of an REC. Only the technical and economic features of REC have been specified so far. Furthermore, grid regulations should be adjusted to the emergence of RECs, with exemp-

tions for small and local community projects or local grid tariffs (e.g. in Austria and France).

In Italy, new legislation¹⁸ entered into force in March 2020, which aimed at partially transposing the *European Renewable Energy Directive*. It limits RECs installations to a capacity of 200 kW.¹⁹ These

Box 1. RES legal Environment in Czech Republic

In the Czech Republic, the lack of support mechanisms (e.g. feed-in tariff mechanisms) and the unclear legislative framework have acted as a barrier for the deployment of RES installations. The National Support Scheme for PV installation was suspended 6 years ago, which impeded significantly the RES progress in the country, as well as the development of prosumership patterns. Amendments to the current legislation are currently being drafted, which are meant to transpose the RED II. However, no operational support scheme for PV technology is currently envisioned, which was considered by experts as a major bottleneck for RECs.

In cases of small and medium-size installations that engage in self-consumption, PV technology is supported by an investment scheme and should remain so in the foreseeable future. In addition, the amendments also propose that a larger installation should also profit from investment support schemes under the EU Modernisation Fund and the ETS Scheme. This could benefit RECs and facilitate such small-scale investments but the major difference between RECs and prosumership also lies in the capacity threshold for the use of the grid: since an energy supplier licence is needed for PV capacity exceeding 10 kW, grid costs would still be financially unbearable for citizens willing to set up a REC.

¹⁸ Decree law of 30 December 2019, no. 162, title III, newly introduced art. 42 bis “Self-consumption from RES.”

¹⁹ For details see Borroni, A., Lowitzsch, J., Tartaglia, A. 2020. Introduzione alle comunità energetiche – quadro normativo di riferimento, misure di attuazione e incentivi. Tutela e Sicurezza del Lavoro, Università degli studi di Milano – Bicocca.

conditions narrow down significantly the scope of communities. In addition, some of the most fundamental aspects of the RED II directive that have to be implemented in national legislation are not being addressed in the new law. The definition of RECs does not emphasise enough the prosuming elements nor the self-organisation of these communities among citizens who are not aiming for financial profit. The new law authorises consumers to aggregate small-scale installations and benefit only from a discount on the utility bills but the installation, in this case, remains under the ownership of the majority investors.

Information Gaps

The **limited and inconsistent information** about opportunities to develop RES ownership models renders access to reliable information extremely difficult. Investments schemes and opportunities to develop more decentralised RES projects are often rather confusing for the consumers to decipher and understand. Moreover, information and possible incentives for potential investors (either companies and SMEs, municipalities or consumers) are scattered through different jurisdictions, institutions and sites, which hardly simplifies the knowledge about different RES-E technologies and funding schemes.

Furthermore, the **inconsistent national competences regarding RES incentives and investment support schemes** across different MS hinders the emergence of a transnational network of expertise. While

RECs generally have a variety of financial resources at their disposal, either directly (i.e. investment supports, bank loans) or indirectly (e.g. through energy efficiency schemes), there is still a lack of knowledge and awareness on how to tap into and benefit from these resources.

Access to Finance

Financing barriers remain one of the main bottlenecks across Europe. This is especially true for vulnerable consumers and in countries or regions with higher energy poverty, e.g. in CEE. The up-front cost of RES makes it very hard for consumers to invest. In addition, the lack of proper information and one-stop-shop structures to advise these disadvantaged consumers further increases the false perception of risk and acts as an impediment to the overcoming of administrative barriers. The access to finance further remains a problem for most countries, either due to of the nature of tax incentives and financial support (e.g. reimbursement for installations instead of downward payment) or because of a complex regulatory framework that discourages potential investors.

In the Czech Republic, for example, where subsidies exist for domestic energy refurbishment, consumers cannot benefit from relevant technical advice and must cover all expenses from the beginning. This partially explains why few people apply for such financial schemes in many countries. Furthermore, financial instruments such as the *European Investment Bank* (EIB) do not cover single investments, as such financing is

Table 2. Existing incentives measures (as of October 2020)

	Type of intervention	Recipient of incentives	Method of remuneration	Energy domain
DE	Energy efficiency	All users	Tax deduction – discounted investment loans	Electricity, Thermal power
	Energy management optimisation	All users	Tax deduction – discounted investment loans	Electricity, Thermal power
	RES	All users	Premium tariffs / Tax deduction	Electricity
	Energy efficiency + RES	Citizens	Premium tariffs / Reimbursement of investment	Electricity, Thermal power
		Business	Tax deduction	Thermal power

	Type of intervention	Recipient of incentives	Method of remuneration	Energy domain
IT	Energy efficiency	All users	Bond issue	Electricity, Thermal power
	Energy management optimisation	All users	Reimbursement of investment	Electricity
	RES	All users	Premium tariffs / Minimum guaranteed prices	Electricity, Thermal power
	Energy efficiency + RES	Citizens, Municipalities	Tax deduction – tax break / Reimbursement of project’s investment	Electricity, Thermal power
	RES + Energy management optimisation	All users	Discount on one or more tariff components that make up the bill	Electricity
	Energy efficiency + Energy management optimisation + RES	All users	Tax deduction – tax break / Reimbursement of investment / Premium tariffs / Reimbursement of project’s investment	Electricity, Thermal power
CZ	RES	All users	Tax deduction – discounted investment loans	Electricity
	Energy management optimisation	Business	Tax deduction – discounted investment loans	Electricity
	Energy efficiency + RES	Citizens	Tax deduction – discounted investment loans	Electricity, Thermal power

Source: Based on detailed classification of incentive measures, developed by Mutani, G., S. Santantonio, J. Lowitzsch, L. Roth, & P. Slevac. (forthcoming) *Economic incentives for energy efficiency measures and low-emissions technologies*.

too small for the standards of the EIB and similar institutions. The lack of expertise on complex financing mechanisms (such as the piloted CSOP), means that the necessary steps and procedures remain a problem for consumers and investors in the initial stages of setting up RES installations.

The transposition of these comprehensive rules in the MSs national legislations – in particular those on energy communities – requires developing, implementing and scaling up investment models that pool the capital participation of consumers in all 27 MSs. The major challenge in this process is the inclusion of local governments and/or commercial investors like SMEs and the move to economies of scale while retaining the benefits of individual consumer participation.²⁰

²⁰ Ibid.

Grid Regulations

One of the most central challenges for RECs lies in the grid connection and the use of the public grid. The administrative and legal process, including the permit application process, can be exceedingly long, unpredictable and costly. Since **RECs act as producers and de facto suppliers at the same time** (through supply contracts or through local sharing and self-consumption), they can take on many forms and perform different services (e.g. service provider, retailer, energy supplier, balancing service provider or even distribution system operator) which vary from one MSs to the other. Energy cooperatives in Northern Italy (esp. in Lombardia, Veneto and Piemonte) stand out as a particular example since the grid they use belongs to the cooperatives that are (correspondingly) obligated to operate and maintain them. In the rest of Italy, cooperatives partially engage in self-consumption and energy selling into the

public grid, thereby bearing an obligation to pay for connection costs.

Securing access to the public grid is vital for RECs, so that they can sell the surplus of electricity, and therefore be financially sustainable. In addition, business risks are increased as connections to the grid can sometimes be refused or substantially delayed due to technical reasons, often without justification or the possibility to contest these decisions. **Current grid regulation**, in most European countries, **works in favour of centralised generation assets**. It does so by not changing certain connection, testing and metering provisions, availability requirements, as well as keeping high administrative costs and minimum size thresholds.²¹ These thresholds and procedures already penalise aggregators of small, distributed assets and make it difficult for pioneers on the ground to compete on an equal footing.

In addition to the costs, the necessary **permits and licensing administrative procedures** are still much cumbersome in most EU countries. This includes not only the number of permits, but also the length of the process, the high-costs and technicalities linked to licensing. Permits for grid connection are mandatory in most MSs and obtaining them often requires

expensive and time-consuming procedures. Furthermore, potential RECs must navigate these procedures with limited access to information on the necessary steps, existing guarantees or fast track procedures. Finally, additional permits such as construction and environmental permits are often required, which makes the whole procedure intimidatingly burdensome. Although private grids can provide a solution to this problem (despite the important costs they represent), the development of a private infrastructure also requires permits and even more complex administrative procedures.²²

Inconsistency with national social policies

Moreover, in many countries, **social policy still poses some incompatibility with RECs**. This calls for an additional focus on the legal implications of participating in a REC for vulnerable consumers (e.g. compatibility with social transfers). The different social policies defined at the national level make the inclusion of vulnerable consumers and reinforcement of their rights, as envisioned by RED II, challenging. The inclusion of low-income consumers in the provision on RECs could create conflicts with existing national legislation on social transfer and welfare.²³ Social wel-

Box 2. Stop-and-go Policy and Unstable Regulatory Framework in Italy and Czech Republic

Concerning RES-E support mechanisms in Italy, the *premium tariff (ritiro dedicato)* and net-metering (*scambio sul posto*) have been strong incentives that unfortunately were not successful in fostering the collaborative enterprises but only supported commercial PV and wind projects. Such support mechanisms have led to unforeseen problems, such as the development of PV installations on agricultural lands because of the profit character of the schemes applied across many regions in Italy. This required parliamentary intervention in order to be halted.

In the Czech Republic, renewable energy was supported through feed-in tariffs and a green bonus until January 2014 when the previous support schemes for RES-E installations were phased out (with the exception of small hydro power plants). Furthermore, the conditions for the remaining RES (e.g. biomass, geothermal) are much stricter (in particular capacity, permit and licensing requirements for the construction, including building permit and date of commissioning), which makes them unattractive for potential investors.

²¹ Eaton. 2019. *Outdated grid regulation slowing Europe's energy transition*, published by EATON on June 21, 2019.

²² SCORE interviews with local experts in the field of renewable energy from the Czech Republic, Germany and Italy.

²³ Lowitzsch, J. & F. Hanke. 2019. Consumer (Co-)ownership in Renewables, Energy Efficiency and the Fight Against Energy Poverty – a Dilemma of Energy Transitions. In: RELP Volume 9, pp. 5-21.

fare legislation across the EU MSs, including in Italy, the Czech Republic and Germany, creates a ‘welfare dilemma as they require social benefit recipients to have no access to asset ownership or income, thus prohibiting their participation in (co-) ownership of RE installations.

EU-wide challenges faced by Renewable Energy Communities

Some of the challenges RECs are facing are rooted in the general framework conditions and status quo of the established electricity system, including network regulations and market access requirements which have favoured large, centralised monopolistic utilities and increased complexity and costs of small-scale producers of RES. Therefore, these joint challenges have to be addressed at an EU-level through a supporting mechanism to guarantee that small RES producers could compete on an equal footing with the big businesses.

The **unequal access to ancillary services and capacity markets, as well as the discriminatory grid regulations** seem to act as major barriers for small-scale RES producers. Many incumbent generators and grid companies are resisting the liberalisation of regulatory measures and the opening up of energy markets to more decentralised forms of ownership.²⁴ Moreover, the loopholes in national legislation and the strong incumbents lobby are used by energy companies to impede the new-entrants and, thus, distort the social elements of a REC. **More inclusive approaches to governance are needed** to make room for new actors

and facilitate a shift from top-down decision making in the energy sector to a more participatory approach with a clear understanding of the role, responsibilities and duties each actor possesses.

Another **challenge is related to the differing legal forms RECs can take**, which creates disparities among MS. According to art. 71 of the RED II the legal status of RECs is defined at the national level and MSs are free to choose any form of entity for renewable energy communities.

The main **technological challenge** here is related to balancing the geographically dispersed, intermittent RES with demand. Complementarity²⁵ is an optimal technical and economic solution for the integration of RES onto the grid.²⁶ Its many benefits include improved grid stability,²⁷ increased network capacity to integrate variable renewable power,²⁸ and reduced system costs for energy storage.²⁹ Prioritizing complementarity serves are key to decreasing not only required RE generation capacity, but also storage and backup requirements.

With an expanding number of small units owned by individuals; governance, control and predictability of the energy markets (where balancing supply and demand and security of supply are crucial) become increasingly complex and thus problematic.³⁰ **The transaction costs associated with integrating new, small or medium sized actors** accompanied by complex regulations is another major challenge for vulnerable consumers. The exemptions from fees and levies for some consumers leads, in many countries, to higher

²⁴ Burke, Matthew, J. and Stephens, Jennie, C. 2018 Political Power and Renewable Energy Futures: A Critical Review. In: *Energy Research & Social Science*, Volume 35.

²⁵ Complementarity among different RES technologies, both over time and spatially, to address RES intermittency and flexibility issues with a synergetic approach. For example, between PV systems and hydroelectric power (PV system used to pump water into reservoirs when demand is low and electricity is cheap in order to store the energy).

²⁶ Hoicka, C.E. & I. Rowlands. 2011. ‘Solar and Wind Resource Complementarity: Advancing Options for Renewable Electricity Integration in Ontario, Canada’. In: *Renewable Energy*, Volume 36, Issue 1.

²⁷ Zhang, X. et. al. 2018. Short-Term Optimal Operation of a Wind-PV-Hydro Complementary Installation: Yalong River, Sichuan Province, China. In: *Energies*. Volume 11, Issue: 4.

²⁸ Wei, S. & G. Harrison. 2019. Wind-Solar Complementarity and Effective Use of Distribution Network Capacity. In: *Applied Energy*. Volume 247.

²⁹ Ramirez C.L. et al. 2019. Potential Analysis of Hybrid Renewable Energy Systems for Self-Sufficient Residential Use in Germany and the Czech Republic. In: *Energies*, Vol. 12, Issue 21.

³⁰ Ibid.

end-prices for the remaining which could have an impact on the acceptance of RES projects. A consequential risk of RED II is that well-off households are more likely to get off the grid and become energy self-sufficient. This will leave poorer communities with a disproportionate burden of paying for the centralised electricity infrastructure. Therefore, poorer households should be actively enabled to participate in and benefit from projects.³¹ Prosumership/participation in RECs should not only be accessible to consumers of a higher socio-economic status.³²

The Challenges for Implementing CSOP model in the Czech Republic, Italy and Germany

Susa Valley (Italy)

Italy possesses an extensive track-record of long-standing historical cooperation in the electricity sectors, with cooperatives that are more than 100 years old. Most of these “energy communities” are found in the Northern part of Italy, in an area called the “Arco Alpino” (stretching from Liguria to Friuli) and have emerged as a result of direct citizen investment in hydroelectric power projects.³³ These initiatives are considered as the closest model to what has been envisioned in the RED II regarding REC.

In the Italian constitution the competence for the production, transmission and distribution of energy are shared between the state and the regions, which resulted in a fragmented regulatory framework. The legal framework does not allow the share of electricity between the members of a cooperative (e.g. enostra). The energy must be fed into the grid be-

fore being redistributed to the members. Cooperatives can fall under the category of energy suppliers in case they sell a part of their production to third parties. The frequent changes in the Italian regulations create uncertainty for potential prosumers.

There are two specific forms of renewable energy communities in Italy:

- **The historical energy cooperatives**, RECs based on legal frameworks established in the 1960s. Some communities co-managed local plants (mainly hydro plants) and developed a local grid, with a point of connection to the national grid;
- **Utility Efficient System** (Sistema Efficiente di Utensila) this applies to installed capacities of up to 20 MW that can consume their produced electricity or sell such electricity to a unique local consumer. This type of installation could be used by large commercial or industrial consumers.

The Piedmont Region was the first Italian region to promote RECs with a regional law.³⁴ Benefiting from this law, a biomass installation with a District Heating Network covering 21 different municipalities was built in the Susa Valley, applying the CSOP model of financing. The investment plans are based on substituting existing heating facilities running on diesel oil and natural gas with new ones using local biomass (wood chips) as a heating source. The users of the public infrastructure became co-owners of the biomass plant and thus turned into prosumers. The energy savings result in a learning effect: as co-owners of the RE installation, the users have an incentive to use less in order to be able to sell more (excess production), which in turn increases funds available for infrastructure. In addition, a regional public municipal sewage and waste company (owned by 37 local municipalities) is considering setting up an energy community applying the CSOP model.

³¹ See Hanke, F. & J. Lowitzsch. 2020. [Empowering Vulnerable Consumers to Join Renewable Energy Communities – Towards an Inclusive Design of the Clean Energy Package](#). In: *Energies* 13, 1615.

³² Ibid.

³³ SCORE interviews with local experts in the field of Renewable Energy, Energy Cooperative and Renewable Energy Communities in Czech Republic, Germany and Italy.

³⁴ Regional Law of Piedmont Region, n. 12 August 3rd 2018: Constitution of energy communities, presented on 24th July 2017 and approved on July 25th 2018 (Istituzione delle comunità energetiche).

After the municipal elections in Italy (May 2019) there was a change of political support in many municipalities for pilots involved in the project, which acted as a barrier slowing down the further development and expansion of RECs in Italy. The circulation of “not-in-my-backyard narratives”³⁵ and the lack of information on this topic has also contributed to the local resistance towards renewable energy cooperatives. The decrease of new RES plants coincides with a period of substantial decline in new investments and projects in Italy as a whole. The strongest opposition can be observed in the northern regions of Italy; Lombardy remains the region with the highest number of contested installations, followed by Tuscany and Lazio. The backlash in the North can be explained by the higher degree of industrialisation and population density, which naturally requires more installations and various types of energy infrastructures. The disapproval was justified as “negative externalities on the quality of life”, followed by “negative externalities for the environment” (in the case of biomass installations) and a lack of citizen inclusion in decision-making. A limited dialogue between citizens and the municipalities interested in new energy installations has also reinforced this trend.

Prague (Czech Republic)

The **regulatory framework in the Czech Republic is under-developed**. In most cases, municipalities are the most active actors in investing and owning RES installations (mostly Wind turbines, Photovoltaics, District Heating Networks with companies under municipalities’ control). Projects involving citizens, businesses and municipalities in a model that would fit the RED II definition of RECs have not been implemented so far in Czechia.³⁶ This can be partly explained by the local and national context: in that the main driver for consumers to invest in RES is financial gain, either through the benefit of additional income or through cheaper electricity prices. Only a small

part of the population justifies their prosumer choices with environmental concerns. The legal framework in the Czech Republic at the present time does not offer enough stability. The weak RE ambition in the Czech National Energy and Climate Action Plan (NECP) and the lack of incentives for green technologies do not provide a favourable regulatory environment for a more decentralised energy transition.

The Czech Republic doubled its RES capacity between 2004 and 2013, after which all support for RES was discontinued, this hampered the development of small-scale RES projects in the country. Since 2014 – 2015, there has been no feed-in tariff support in the Czech Republic. Concerning small-scale energy projects, the only support scheme is investment support that can be obtained through a state contribution for building a small-scale domestic installation. This is mainly used by family houses and covers 1000 to 2000 installations per year. The scheme requires upfront payments by the households, which can be reimbursed at a later stage, making it difficult for low-income consumers to use such incentives. The complex administrative process for RES deployment, including requirements for different permits and licenses, is another bottleneck for the development of community-owned RES sources.

In the past years, Czech Republic has only installed 25 MW of PV installations, mostly concerning self-consumption projects.³⁷ The city of Hostětín in Moravia has been using forest biomass (woodchip) for district heating, supplying all households in the village.³⁸

The awarding of special bank loans backed by a government program for promoting the development of PV installations at favourable interest rates could provide a good solution to remove this important investment barrier for vulnerable consumers.³⁹ Moreover, the split incentive remains a further issue: most low-income tenants do not own their house. For

³⁵ Blanchetti, Emilia and Seminar, Simona. (2018) *‘L’era del Dissenso’*, Osservatorio Nimby Forum, XIII edition.

³⁶ SCORE interviews with local experts in the field of renewable energy from the Czech Republic, Germany and Italy.

³⁷ Ibid.

³⁸ [Hostětín Municipality’s Official Website](#), Hostětín Municipality.

³⁹ Ibid.

these reasons, the main beneficiaries of RES projects involving vulnerable consumers are generally municipal buildings, in which the municipality can cover the upfront investments costs to install RES-E to, in turn, provide electricity to the tenants at a cheaper price. Even in such cases, the need for a direct connection to the grid can still pose a major barrier, since every flat has a “consumers point” along with an electricity meter. Since the public grid operator owns all the connections, it is virtually impossible to connect the RES installation to this connection point without refurbishing the entire building and forming a new connection from the roof to each, individual flat. Even if this is possible in theory, the financial and administrative costs are overwhelming and make such co-ownership form practically impossible.

The Czech capital, the city of Prague has a population of 1.3 million and is currently finalizing the Climate Plan with the aim of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 45% by 2030, where, among other things, one of the important priorities is the development of community renewables. Prague plans to produce more than 8% of total energy consumption from renewable sources by the end of 2030. In the coming years, it is expected to increase the installed capacity on all long-term city property (municipal and city buildings, apartment buildings, local entrepreneurs, etc.) with a total production of energy from renewable sources of approximately 2.1 GWh per year. Excess energy will be used for public, office and private buildings and energy savings from changes in consumption behavior are expected to reach up to 10%. The pilot project will be implemented in the period 2021 – 2022 also thanks to support from the SCORE project, when photovoltaic panels with an output of 2-3 MWp will be installed on city and mostly school buildings.

Essen (Germany)

Germany is a pioneer in Europe regarding the spread of energy communities and one of the countries with the highest share in citizen financial participation. Germany’s current REC landscape has emerged from a grassroots movement which has led to a structural shift in the ownership models of the country’s electricity market and its citizens’ energy consumption patterns. Despite the existence of various ownership models, in 2018 only 5% of the installed RES capacity was owned by large, centralized energy utilities.⁴⁰

In Germany, the central legislation addressing prosuming is the *Renewable Energy Sources Act* (Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz, hereinafter EEG, adopted in 2000 and amended several times), which defines the term as ‘self-consumption’. The legislation covers only the term “citizen energy” (Bürgerenergie) encompassing the EU legal definition of an energy community⁴¹ and characteristics of RECs. This definition refers to a community consisting of at least 10 natural persons who hold at least 51% of voting rights collectively and in which not more than 10% of voting rights are held individually.

Energy communities in Germany can take various legal forms (such as cooperatives, associations, LLCs, etc). In Germany, the legal definition of “citizen energy companies” could serve as a basis for the definition of REC,⁴² with modifications concerning the spatial delimitation of generation and shared use such as connection between rural regions and urban centres with high consumption levels or close spatial connection between generation and consumption for the joint regional use of electricity by the members of the community. Although REC members are allowed to receive return on investments, the REC is conceived to provide ecological, economic or social benefits in a given area and not to have a profit-oriented character.

⁴⁰ Bertram, R. & R. Primova (eds). 2018. *Energy Atlas 2018: Figures and Facts about Renewables in Europe*, Heinrich Boll Stiftung.

⁴¹ Campos, I. et. al. 2020. *Regulatory challenges and opportunities for collective renewable energy prosumers in the EU*. In: *Energy Policy*, Volume 138.

⁴² Hauneke, F. & S. Nitzsche. 2020 *Impulspapier Energy Sharing*, Berlin: Energy Brainpool.

As the RED II has not yet been transposed, the only existing incentive to consume RE is self-consumption. The right to energy-sharing that is enshrined in RED II still needs to be introduced in Germany. The payment of the EEG surcharge (renewable surcharge),⁴³ accounting and contract drafting are hurdles that further complicate the energy sharing. Furthermore, the direct selling of electricity from EEG systems is subject to certain technical conditions according to the EEG, which are difficult to meet for small systems. Finally, low-income households face financial barriers to REC participation. Low minimum deposits or options to pay in instalments should be developed as solutions for such vulnerable investors.⁴⁴

The draft legislative amendments to EEG include new connection regulations for the post-EEG systems and the design of tenders for PV roof systems, while adapting the legal framework of PV systems to allow the sale of solar power to the grid operators for the market price minus marketing costs of 0,2 ct/kWh for a transitional period. To promote a market-driven expansion of RES across the country and to integrate the objectives of the *German Climate Protection Program 2030* in the amendments, the draft law foresees specific expansion paths for all technologies: PV should be increased to 100GW (twice the current national installed capacity) and 91 GW for wind power (onshore and offshore). Certain technologies will be promoted in tenders up to 2028.

The government envisions the introduction of tenders for PV systems from 2021 until 2028, with an increase in quantities from 2025. The tenders foresee the installation of 200 MW of rooftop PV systems in 2021. This volume should then increase in the following years to reach 1.2 GW in 2028. The introduction of more tender categories could be considered an improvement, since rooftop PV systems had to compete directly in tenders for installing capacity above 750 kW.

Some of the EU requirements regarding the removal of disproportionate and discriminatory charges, which would imply that the intended exemption from taxes and surcharges, has not been fully reflected in the amendments. For example, the PV tenant electricity scheme should include remuneration for large PV tenant electricity projects. The current draft legislation foresees a surcharge of 1.42 cents/kWh for systems up to 750kW and 2.66 cents/kWh for small projects (<10kW).

Despite the current regulatory environment in Germany which is supportive towards self-consumption and individual prosumers but does not particularly facilitate renewable energy communities, there are some good examples of community projects that have spread in the country and showcase innovative financial and technical solutions for collective self-consumption, some of which also involved vulnerable consumers.

The city of Essen plans to apply the CSOP model on the campus of the Franz Sales Haus and the adjacent Vocational College East. Three types of stakeholders are involved in this project: the municipality of Essen; the sponsoring association of the Franz Sales Haus; and the sports club on campus. A total of around EUR 340,000 is to be invested in roof-supported PV systems, mainly on the Vocational College East (approx. 225 kWp) and on three buildings on the campus of the Franz Sales House (approx. 140 kWp). About 30% of the investment should be financed from own resources and 70% could be financed by loans. The *Vocational College East* has very suitable roof areas ensuring a maximum capacity of more than 300kWp, while the Franz Sales Haus has an area network with a total of 15 connected buildings and a commercial load profile with an enormous capacity to absorb additional electricity. This complementarity makes it possible to build

⁴³ Under the Renewable Energy Sources Act (in German), the remuneration rates that German power plants receive from producing RES power and feeding it into the grid are set for 20 years. EEG surcharge refers to the difference between the specified feed-in tariffs paid under the EEG and the sale of the RE at the EEX energy exchange by the grid operators (see [State-imposed components of the electricity price](#), Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy).

⁴⁴ Eckhardt, S. 2020. [Rechtsgutachten: Geplante EEG-Novelle verstößt bei Photovoltaik-Eigenverbrauch gegen Europarecht](#), PV Magazine, 12 October.

a larger system that can enable 100% self-consumption. The Franz Sales Haus owns its own microgrid, which allows it to avoid the corresponding costs and surcharges that would be due if the energy would be shared via the public grid.

Policy recommendations

For tackling many of the political, administrative, financial, technical and disinformation challenges, solutions at both the national and EU-level are needed. The new RED II guarantees EU energy citizens a certain set of rights, however, its transposition into national legal frameworks could both enable and burden the process. In order to reap the social and economic benefits of RECs, a specific strategy must be deployed aiming at understanding the needs of the local communities, identifying the stakeholders, as well as defining what would be the best way to reach out to vulnerable consumers and engage them.

Recommendations for the transposition of the RED II Directive⁴⁵

- Legislators should define various categories of proximity depending on the spatial organisation of an REC and local needs taking into account geographies of energy supply and demand, urbanisation trends, demographics of investment and heterogeneity of REC membership.
- Lawmakers should specifically support business models like CSOPs that make renewable investments compatible for municipalities and local SMEs while allowing strategic partnerships with commercial investments that can scale RECs while limiting incumbent control.
- To provide access for RECs to funding under the general EU financing sources, it is crucial to include them now in the operational programmes defining their requisites for participation; this will also

safeguard a policy dialogue on key issues of programme implementation and performance.

- The upcoming MFF and Next Generation EU funding mechanism shall consider including stronger target support measures for citizen-led energy projects and a requirement for national governments to set up a certain ratio for micro grants and decentralised citizens' projects. National governments should be required to enable and facilitate such citizen-led projects in line with Article 25 of the proposal for a Regulation laying down common provisions on the ERDF, ESF + and EMFF.
- Measures in the National Recovery and Resilience Plans (NRRs) should prioritise green and sustainable investments (e.g., the "ECO Bonus 110%" of the Decreto Rilancio of 15 May 2020) which can become an important complementary financing source.

Recommendations for national policy-makers

- National policymakers have to adopt specific measures to ensure that all consumers, including those in low-income or vulnerable households or in social housing could participate in renewable energy communities.
- In view of the new EU Strategy called "*A renovation wave for Europe*" as part of the *European Green Deal*, national governments shall propose specific measures to promote the role of energy communities in the implementation of energy efficiency policies and measures, such as the energy efficiency obligation schemes and alternative measures under Article 7 of the EED, the long-term strategy for the renovation of public and private residential and commercial buildings, as well as the promotion of energy services in the public sector.
- Community-based criteria should be further clarified in the procurement of energy services by local

⁴⁵ Most of the recommendations for the transposition of the RED II Directive are based on the transposition guidelines formulated in: PROSEU, *Community Power*, SCORE, *Renewables Networking Platform*, EREF 2020: *Transposition Guidance for citizen energy policies* – Recommendations to strengthen prosumers and energy communities when transposing the Clean Energy Package (RED II, IEMD); See also Hoicka, C.E., J. Lowitzsch, M.C. Brisbois, A.Kumar, L. Ramirez Camargo. 2021 forthcoming. Implementing a just renewable energy transition: Policy advice for transposing the new European rules for Renewable Energy Communities; In: Energy Policy.

authorities and community projects should benefit from targeted support schemes:

- o National governments should consider designing **electricity sharing schemes** tailored to the needs of the households in order to facilitate joint household renewable energy projects.
- o Procedures for **introducing net-metering possibilities** for small-scale RES should be simplified and regulation should prevent DSOs from arbitrary changes to the administrative procedures for trading excess electricity with the grid.
- o **Expanding the focus of the RES policies** from electricity-only to heating and cooling as well – with the proper incentives for end-users to consider such options.
- o MSs should encourage RE “clusters” that **support complementarity between RES amongst a range of actors** in order to minimize costs and maximize benefits of RES integration.
- o Special attention should be paid to Art. 18 of the RED II Directive on **information and training**, which is a key component for enabling citizens and communities to become active players on the energy markets. National policy-makers and implementing agencies shall develop plans for wide and targeted communication activities and capacity building programmes to increase the awareness of the citizens on these opportunities.
- o The installation of small RES at end-consumers’ locations should be promoted through **one-stop shops** at municipalities and administrative burdens should be reduced.
- o **Energy poverty should be prioritised** in the policy frameworks of the energy and environment ministries, in close cooperation with the social policy ministries at national level.
- o MSs should implement a framework for vulnerable households in the process of transposition of RED II. Actions to **address energy poverty and vulnerability** should include incentives for affected citizens to participate.
- o National governments need to design a concrete action plan for jumpstarting **investments in small-scale renewable energy plants** that includes a piloting phase for a new support scheme in several municipalities to be followed up by a nation-wide program.
- o The relevant national ministries and agencies shall consider relationships between the spatial distribution of RES potential, community density and demand, and demographics with the aim to **maximize both social acceptance and investments** in RECs.